

Nature identification and gender spill-over: an intersectional analysis of Umeå's local climate policy

Angelica Lundgren & Annica Kronsell

To cite this article: Angelica Lundgren & Annica Kronsell (23 May 2025): Nature identification and gender spill-over: an intersectional analysis of Umeå's local climate policy, Local Environment, DOI: [10.1080/13549839.2025.2506604](https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2025.2506604)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2025.2506604>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

Published online: 23 May 2025.

Submit your article to this journal [↗](#)

Article views: 548

View related articles [↗](#)

View Crossmark data [↗](#)

Citing articles: 2 View citing articles [↗](#)

Nature identification and gender spill-over: an intersectional analysis of Umeå's local climate policy

Angelica Lundgren and Annica Kronsell

School of Global Studies, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden

ABSTRACT

The local level is increasingly recognized as crucial to the climate transition. National level climate objectives are often delegated by governments to be implemented by public authorities at the local level, and many of the actions required to reach climate objectives concern areas where municipalities have jurisdiction. We study the climate policies of Umeå, a municipality in Sweden. While most Swedish municipalities have developed climate policies, many have done so in line with an ecomodern logic of climate governance which means they have been slow to recognize the need to include all dimensions of sustainability. Using an intersectional approach, this article explored if and how social and ecological dimensions are embedded in local climate policies. We found that Umeå had taken an ambitious approach, including both ecological and social sustainability in interesting ways. Umeå stands out for prioritizing the inherent worth of nature beyond its utilitarian benefits and connecting it to the city's identity. Our material attested to a long-standing commitment to gender integration which spilled over to allow for the consideration of other social groups in efforts to advance social sustainability.

Key Policy Highlights

- Swedish Climate governance mostly works from an ecomodern governance logic but Umeå is an exception.
- Umeå has ambitiously included both ecological and social sustainability in climate governance.
- The case of Umeå shows that it is possible to prioritize nature when it is connected to the city's identity.
- Commitment to integrate gender in policy making can pave the way for the inclusion of other social groups and perspectives.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 7 October 2024

Accepted 3 May 2025

KEYWORDS

Social and ecological sustainability; municipal policy; policy making; intersectionality

1. Introduction

Climate change is among the most pressing issues of the twenty-first century and cities are increasingly recognized to have a crucial role in making the climate transition happen (cf. Bulkeley 2010; Castán Broto and Bulkeley 2013; Kern 2019; Otto et al. 2021).

CONTACT Angelica Lundgren Box 700, 405 30 Göteborg, Sweden

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group
This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

Climate objectives are often delegated by governments to be implemented at the local level, and many of the actions required to reach climate objectives concern areas where local public authorities, i.e. municipalities, have jurisdiction. In Sweden, municipalities wield a significant degree of autonomy, with decision making power and control over finances. Notably relevant to the climate transition is their authority over city planning, housing, energy – and transport provision, as well as the social, health and education sectors. Most municipalities in Sweden have developed climate policies, and some are also considered leading in performance (Emelianoff 2014; Kern 2019). We are interested in how municipalities “think” and act on the social and ecological dimensions in their climate policy making. At the same time, noting that the social dimension and the attention to human-nature relations of climate policy, has to date been insufficient.

In previous work, we analysed local climate policy and policymaking in the two cities and municipalities of Gothenburg and Malmö. We applied a critical feminist intersectional perspective (Rask, Lundgren, and Kronsell 2025) and found that both cities tackled climate policy similarly and much was lacking regarding the social dimension. Public authorities tend to adhere to an eco-modern logic of climate governance (Kronsell 2024)¹ which can interfere with the need to include the full range of sustainability in policies: not only economic, but also ecological and social sustainability (Brundtland 1987). The aim of this article is to explore how social and ecological dimensions are implemented in local climate policies.

To achieve this aim, we apply an intersectional lens capable of generating critical and constructive insights inherent in climate policy (Kajiser and Kronsell 2014; Kronsell et al. 2023). This lens aids in discerning the power relations embedded in climate policies in terms of what categories of humans and nature are deemed relevant and how, what knowledges are considered significant, and what social norms are prevalent. This article focuses on Umeå, which has taken an ambitious and unique approach to sustainability, excelling in both social and ecological aspects. In the ambition to learn from its approach, we ask how Umeå envisions climate policy in relation to issues of equity, equality and human-nature relations. Using the case of Umeå, this article has the dual purpose of exploring the implementation of socio-ecological, human-nature relations in municipal policy-making while also illustrating how an intersectional lens can be applied to local public policy.

Swedish cities are politically organized into municipalities with an elected municipal council responsible for the overarching municipal strategy and budget. Municipalities have a comparatively high degree of autonomy, taxation power and responsibility for planning and services in the social sector (Persson 2013) enabling them to enact environmental and climate strategies that surpass those set at the national level. Although this study focuses on a municipality in Sweden the intersection of equity and sustainability in climate policy is of general importance. The findings of this study should be applicable not only to various city sizes but also to similar initiatives in different countries.

The article begins by showing how this study contributes to existing research, then we introduce the case of Umeå. Following this, we outline our theoretical framework of intersectionality and the methods and material that the analysis is based on. The focus of the analysis is on how policy and policy makers vision and enact, first, ecological, human-to-nature relations and secondly, the social, human-to-human power relation. From the analysis we conclude that Umeå is ambitious and has included ecological and social

sustainability in interesting ways. It stands out for prioritizing the worth of nature and connecting it to the city's identity. The attention to social aspects is advanced via a long-standing commitment to gender integration believed to open for the consideration of other social groups.

2. Previous literature

This paper contributes to several fields of research. First, to research that has stressed the interconnectedness of social and ecological sustainability arguing for the need to address equity and justice in climate action and policy. The importance of addressing structural questions of equity and justice in climate action became particularly prominent with the 2018 IPCC 1.5 Degrees Special Report which emphasized the need for climate action to align with the Sustainable Development Goals “leaving no one behind” (IPCC 2018). Thus, recognizing that vulnerability to climate change varies among societal groups (Arora-Jonsson 2011; IPCC Report 2022; Thomas et al. 2019) due to differences in gender, class, race, geographical location, etc. – known as intersectional factors (Cuomo 2011; Kaijser and Kronsell 2014). This recognition is crucial because climate change is likely to disproportionately affect the most vulnerable in society and exacerbate existing social issues as the most vulnerable are often the least heard in decision-making processes (Hess and McKane 2021; Klinsky et al. 2017; Mummery and Mummery 2019; Westman and Broto 2021). Thus, it accentuates that equity and equality concerns should be incorporated into climate strategies not only to ensure that the policies are democratic and inclusive but also as a preventive effort to avoid differential effects on vulnerable groups when policy is implemented. Our research indicates that there are opportunities to address social issues and that an intersectional approach may provide guidance on how to achieve this.

Secondly, other research has highlighted the important role of cities and municipalities in climate change strategies (Sippel and Jenssen 2009; Collier 1997; cf. Bulkeley and Kern 2006; Otto et al. 2021; Kern 2019; Lundqvist, Lennart, and Kasa 2016). Apart from a few exceptional cases, to date, equity and justice concerns have not been sufficiently incorporated in climate change plans and efforts (Hess and McKane 2021; Khan, Hildingsson, and Garting 2020; Westman and Broto 2021). While scholars have observed an increasing focus on these matters (O'Donnell and Doyon 2023) many cities still lack a comprehensive approach to address them (Hess and McKane 2021). Our case can add to these studies but also be an inspiration for other cities and show how intersectionality can aid in the understanding of holistic climate policy.

Results from the research project *Climate policy and intersectionality: Ways towards a socially inclusive sustainability*² on climate decision-making in public institutions at the national³ as well as local levels in Sweden, indicate that only with difficulty have public authorities been able to consider social justice issues. Our previous research revealed both a lack of awareness about the relevance of and a reluctance to take on social and equity aspects in public institutions. Climate strategies aimed at achieving the goal of a fossil-free welfare state primarily concentrated on technological advancements, explained as a consequence of path-dependencies of eco-modernization (Magnusdóttir, Gunnhildur, and Kronsell 2021), and to major challenges for public sector institutions to conceptualize social equity in relation to their defined tasks related to their remit (Kronsell et al.

2023; Singleton et al. 2022; Singleton and Magnusdottir 2021). In analysis of climate efforts of two larger Swedish municipalities, Gothenburg and Malmö, research pointed to similar problems. While civil servants were committed to climate action and to sustainability, institutional logics, in part rooted in an eco-modern, technocratic, and de-politicised understanding of climate issues and in part a bureaucratic logic of sectorization, impeded a transition that would be in line with the holistic character of climate change and the inclusion of different dimensions of sustainability (Lundgren 2022; Rask 2022; Rask, Lundgren, and Kronsell 2025). In an effort to extend the number of municipalities studied in the project, we found Umeå had taken a different approach and thus selected it for further study.

Finally, we rely on research that considers the importance of language and its expression in policy in terms of the ways that issues are framed, e.g. as problems and solutions (Bacchi 1999; 2012). The language employed in policy and planning signals which issues are assigned importance but also impacts how issues are tackled. Hence, the way policy frames issues of equity when public institutions deal with climate issues can potentially perpetuate existing power imbalances and impede equity efforts. Schlosberg (2013) highlights how framings of justice issues influence professionals' practical engagement with these concerns. Framings can gradually solidify into institutional values and norms that direct governance practices and become significant for outcomes. Ambiguities or vague terminology can impact the effectiveness of equity initiatives; thus, strategies need to be firmly rooted in a comprehensive understanding of systemic injustices and intersectionality (Bradley 2009; O'Donnell and Doyon 2023). An intersectional approach emphasizes the importance of recognizing diverse ways of knowing, thereby challenging unidirectional and hegemonic knowledge creation and dissemination (Collins 2019). Such forms of knowledge imposition risks excluding diverse knowledges, particularly indigenous and locally rooted, and hinder the co-creation of knowledge (Castán Broto and Neves Alves 2018). In this study, we approach climate policy in terms of how social equity and human-nature relations are framed, advocating for an inclusive approach that promotes the reciprocal exchange of knowledge. By foregrounding these perspectives, policies can better address the nuanced and intersecting realities of different communities, ensuring that policies do not merely serve the status quo but foster inclusive, sustainable solutions (Collins 2019; Sievers et al. 2024).

3. Introducing the case: Umeå

Umeå was selected as our case study for several reasons. We wanted to study a Swedish city in the Northern part of Sweden, with a different geography, industrial structure and lower population density.⁴ After reviewing the climate agenda of four Swedish cities; Skellefteå, Kiruna and Karlstad, we chose Umeå for its relatively ambitious approach to climate issues and to social and ecological sustainability. Umeå is the largest city in northern Sweden and the 11th largest municipality in Sweden.⁵ The municipality currently has over 130,000 inhabitants and is a fast-growing city that has more than doubled its population in the past 50 years (RKA 2022). Umeå has high ambitions. Umeå's goal to reach net zero emissions within the municipality by 2040, is to be achieved five years ahead of the Swedish national goals (Amrén and Hedfors 2023). The climate contract 2030, a multilevel agreement where all parties are dedicated to contributing to increasing the pace of

climate change mitigation (Shabb and McCormick 2023) attests to this. Umeå is also one of 52 pilot cities selected by the European Commission to participate in the NetZeroCities Pilot Cities (Laestander 2024).

Umeå has paid attention to both environmental and social sustainability of climate issues in the past. Laestander confirmed that Umeå's ambitions extend into social sustainability as "during the transition toward climate neutrality, Umeå emphasises cooperation through co-creation and dialogue-processes, with the aim to anchor structural change with citizens, civil society and companies operating in Umeå." (2022, 55).

Additional factors suggest that Umeå has prioritized social issues. According to the EU social progress index⁶ the region of Sweden, in which Umeå is located, has the single highest total progress scores in the EU, an index that is measured across three categories: basic human needs, foundations of wellbeing, and opportunity. Within these categories both social sustainability (such as, personal rights, health and wellness, tolerance, and inclusion) and ecological sustainability (such as environmental quality, water, and sanitation) are covered. Additionally, Umeå is home to the sixth largest university in Sweden and has a highly educated population compared to the Swedish average. Umeå has both lower unemployment and crime rate than the national average (Vanhuysen et al. 2022) Thus, we argue that Umeå municipality can serve as a most likely case as it has a solid foundation to implement both socially and ecologically ambitious initiatives.

3.1 An intersectional lens on local climate policy and policy making

This section develops the intersectional lens, a comprehensive analytic approach that allows for a nuanced understanding of the interconnected social and environmental factors and relations at play in local climate policies. Our study centres on how the social and ecological dimensions are implemented in local climate policies, and the intersectional lens helps in understanding how municipalities conceptualize and engage with nature and different social groups. An intersectional lens helps the researcher to get sight of hidden power relations and facilitates the generation of critical insights that, in turn, can contribute to the formulation of constructive ideas for a more inclusive and just climate transition. The framework proposes that how such dimensions are implemented within the local context is intricately tied to power relations in the dynamics of policy implementation for example across actors and policy levels. Originating in feminist theory, intersectionality offers a critical examination of power relations serving as a valuable lens in assessing the potential of municipal climate policymaking to harmonize with both social and environmental sustainability (Kaijser and Kronsell 2014; Kronsell et al. 2023). While intersectional analysis is gaining prominence, its application in policy and policy institutions is less common. We begin with a brief introduction to intersectionality then we show how this lens can be used to study of municipal policies.

Intersectionality starts in the assumption that individuals are part of intersecting power relations and power structures (Collins and Bilge 2016; Lykke 2010; Yuval-Davis 2006). According to Godfrey and Torres, the nexus between intersectional injustices and climate issues is rooted in linked systemic problems (2016a) associated with power hierarchies that are intersectional. Gender, class, race, and age are common examples of social categories but they seldom stand alone. The concept of "energy poverty" used in the EU⁷ to connote energy vulnerability, can serve as an illustrative example. Energy poverty is

typically framed as an issue affecting the economically disadvantaged evoking the category class. Yet those most affected are often older women – an intersection that is less frequently acknowledged. Class, gender and age interact to produce energy vulnerability but only class is recognized through poverty. The other dimensions of power contributing to energy vulnerability remain largely invisible.

Intersectional analysis highlights injustices in terms of identifying the multiple power relations that render certain groups more vulnerable and affected but can also shed light on which groups are privileged. The importance of social categories to an intersectional lens prompts questions about who is unable to speak, act or engage, and who bears the brunt of exclusion and conversely raises questions about who has a voice in and is privileged by climate policy making. Social inequalities manifest differently depending on contextual and historical factors, thus recognizing these differences is crucial when addressing vulnerabilities in local policy (Anthias 2013). Municipal climate policy formulation is predominantly managed by a privileged group – policymakers. The focus of this study is not on policymakers but the social categories of vulnerability and privilege they conceive in and create through policymaking.

Existing intersectional research has mainly studied vulnerable social groups with a primary focus on human-to-human relations. To assess whether the ecological dimension of climate issues have been considered in policy, it is crucial to examine how human-nature relations are conceived in policy. Intersectional scholarship, emerging from social theory, has given less attention to this aspect and must be supplemented by other scholarly work of environmentalists, ecofeminists, and post-humanists who have demonstrated how historical power relations between humans and nature have led to a perceived superiority of humans, enacted through modernity, science, rationality, and technology, endorsing an instrumental view on nature (Merchant 1980; Plumwood 1993). In policy, this is conventionally expressed with nature perceived as a passive, inert entity free to be exploited by humans and society. Nature is denied subjectivity and agency, absorbing nature into the human world often within the framework of technological progress and economic development (Fremaux and Barry 2019). Pla-Julián and Guevara (2019) emphasize the complex interplay between social, environmental, and ethical factors, arguing that sustainability efforts require intentional strategies that recognize this interconnectedness. We believe that including human-nature relations broadens the analysis of relevant power relations and is essential for a more comprehensive understanding of the relation between climate policy and policy making on socio-ecological inequities (cf. Castán Broto and Westman 2019; Gaard 2010; 2011; Thompson and MacGregor 2017).

The development of intersectional theory suggests another broadened focus from social groups to institutional levels where social categories and power relations are embedded (Godfrey and Torres 2016; Winker and Degele 2011). Taking cue from Joan Acker's work, it becomes evident that policy institutions such as municipalities can produce and perpetuate inequalities through institutional or organizational "practices, processes, actions and meanings ... [that] result in and maintain class, gender and racial inequalities" (Acker 2006, 443). Hence, underscoring the need for intersectional analysis in policy institutions (Magnusdóttir, Gunnhildur, and Kronsell 2023) whereby we can detect how intersectional power practices unfold in institutional contexts such as municipal public authorities.

3.2 Analysing power in policy with an intersectional lens

Applying an intersectional lens to the study of local climate change policies involves a multi-faceted analysis. We scrutinize policies and actions by inquiring about which humans, or non-humans are deemed relevant, vulnerable, marginalized, capable, or privileged. Such considerations are not always explicit in policy documents, requiring the researcher to delve deeper to unearth normative underpinnings for example by exploring how the climate change problem is framed and what texts reveal about problems and solutions. Problem frames, articulated in policy, not only suggest actions that should or should not be taken but also point to the eco-social categories deemed relevant or irrelevant within these frames (Bacchi 2012; Bacchi and Eveline 2010). When frames on equity or justice are not explicit or deliberate, power imbalances might be overlooked and persist, impeding equity efforts (Arora-Jonsson and Wahlström 2023, 2). For example, generalized and one-size-fits-all framings might weaken equity as it may fail to cater to the unique aspects of various groups and contexts (O'Donnell and Doyon 2023). Thus, acknowledging and integrating diverse knowledge systems, perspectives, and practices in the framing of policy, can aid in achieving a more comprehensive understanding of eco-social power relations in climate policy.

Framings of nature and social aspects and relations, reveal underlying norms of policy institutions highly relevant for which voices are heard and allowed to influence policy-making processes. The norms embedded in policy documents rest on underlying assumptions that govern groups and society. Some norms are particularly dominant and point to entrenched power relations. Our approach allows for a deeper examination of the underlying norms in framings on human to human as well as human to nature relations, which then are formulated and acted out upon in municipal climate policy.

Thus, when applying the intersectional lens to municipal climate policy we seek to answer the main question: How are categories of humans and nature constructed as relevant within climate policy and its implementation, and what implications does this have for equity and justice? By scrutinizing these relationships, we can better understand and address the underlying power dynamics that impact equity and justice in climate policy and planning. To explore this question in depth we approach climate policy and policy making in terms of how problems are framed. This means asking about which vulnerabilities are recognized, whose experiences and what knowledges are deemed relevant or marginalized, and what dominant norms about human-nature relations shape these framings. This approach allows us to critically assess how intersectional inequalities are embedded within climate governance and planning processes, shedding light on both inclusion and exclusion mechanisms that influence policy outcomes.

4. Methods and material

Building on our prior research conducted at both local and national levels in Sweden, we have identified this method as effective for engaging with the complex nature of diverse, intersecting social and ecological issues. Our approach includes a critical policy analysis of several municipal documents, as well as semi-structured expert interviews with government officials. Policy and planning documents are valuable tools for assessing how cities address different issues and are significant to policymakers and in policy making

processes. Policy documents offer insights on how a municipality perceives the relationship between equity and sustainability. Policy and planning documents are often an outcome of processes that include both conflicts and compromises, while they indicate what is deemed relevant and what is not, they do not always translate into action (for a variety of reasons, which we will not dig deeper into). Thus, only analysing policy documents falls short in an analysis of a city's approach to climate issues (Finn and McCormick 2011; Hess and McKane 2021). To address this limitation, this study triangulates policy analysis with expert interviews and comparative insights from previous research conducted in other Swedish cities and at the national level. While this is not a comparative study per se, these previous insights help situate the case within a broader policy landscape and provide background knowledge for understanding municipal approaches to climate policy. Interviews with policymakers provide a deeper understanding of the policy process and implementation, revealing challenges, negotiations, and institutional path dependencies that may not be visible by solely studying written policies. This combined approach strengthens the analysis by capturing both formal policy frameworks and the realities of its execution.

The goal of this paper is to explore how Umeå's policy strategies deal with (1) justice toward the environment (considering non-human entities and their needs and agency), and (2) justice towards humans (acknowledging different social groups, needs, and knowledges). For the critical policy analysis, we collected policy documents related to social and ecological sustainability from Umeå Municipality. These documents were also verified by the interview participants as being central to their work (Table 1). Four documents from Umeå municipality were chosen:

Already at this point in our analysis we found that although we set out to analyse climate documents, through our interviews we became aware that the municipality worked with different policy documents – on environment, climate and sustainability – interchangeably and also perceived these policies to deal with closely related, even similar issues. They found them instrumental for addressing the intersection between equity and sustainability and as we will see, they also connected them to strategies on mainstreaming.

Through qualitative coding of the four documents listed, we identified dominant framings of human-nature and human-human relations within Umeå's climate policy relating to equity and justice. Themes were extracted using inductive and deductive coding. Initial analysis followed a deductive approach based on prior research, with new categories added as they emerged. Themes were analysed using QDA Miner software. The results

Table 1. Policy documents analysed.

Name	Description
(Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2020).	Umeå's environmental goals that provide a framework for ecological sustainability in the local context.
(Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2022)	Action plan for the environmental goals 2022-2025. It emphasizes social sustainability to a greater extent than the goals themselves, advocating for a holistic, systemic approach.
(Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2022)	Umeå Climate Action Programme. A climate roadmap to guide collective entities (organizations, companies, and public bodies), outlining collective commitment to the Paris Agreement and the climate transition.
(Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2018)	Assessment of the Agenda 2030 implementation, providing a comprehensive evaluation of collaborative efforts.

from this document analysis guided the creation of a semi-structured interview guide, including questions on the participant's perceptions, visions, opportunities, and barriers of social and ecological sustainability. The guide was extensive and open-ended, with the interview direction shaped by participants' answers to reveal what they considered significant. Four expert interviews were conducted online between October and December 2023. Participants were selected to include government officials working on social and ecological sustainability in Umeå municipality, primarily recruited online (municipal website, LinkedIn, etc.). Additionally, a snowballing technique was used to identify additional participants at the end of each interview. While the number of interviews is modest, it reflects the concentrated nature of expertise and decision-making in Umeå's municipal climate governance. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who received written and oral information about the study, its purpose, and confidentiality assurances as per social science ethical guidelines. Interviews were recorded, transcribed, anonymized, and analysed using the same method and software as the policy documents. The second analysis was conducted by comparing (a) the different information from interviewees answers, and (b) information in documents and interviews, to identify connections and/or conflicts / differences.

5. Analysis

Comparing Umeå's policy documents with those of two other municipalities, Malmö and Gothenburg (Rask, Lundgren, and Kronsell 2025), shows Umeå differs in several respects. Malmö and Gothenburg's climate strategies largely follow an eco-modern logic with mostly a technocratic, managerial, and efficiency-oriented framing of social issues (cf. Hagbert, Wangel, and Broms 2020, 211). Umeå intertwines social, economic, and ecological sustainability, repeatedly emphasizing their interconnections and Umeå puts much less emphasis on economic gains and efficiency. Notably, social sustainability is a consistent emphasis across Umeå's documents to a larger degree than we have seen before.

The work in the municipality is guided by four overarching goals frequently referenced in both documents and interviews: First, Umeå has set forth a comprehensive vision for its future development, aiming for sustainable growth in all aspects of society. This vision encompasses social, ecological, economic, and cultural sustainability. Secondly, by the year 2050, the city aims to accommodate 200,000 residents while ensuring that it does not create inequities and segregation in the city. Third, Umeå is committed to fostering gender equality, striving to empower both women and men to actively shape society and their own lives. Lastly, the city has set an ambitious target to achieve climate neutrality by 2040, further underlining its dedication to environmental sustainability. The strive for social and ecological sustainability are highly implicated in these four goals.

5.1 Ecological, human-to-nature power relations

Our analysis addressed how nature is deemed relevant to climate change by approaching policy and interviews through questions about the perceptions of the relation between human and nature and what aspects and norms appear important. We found that what sets Umeå's stance on climate issues apart from that of other cities is how they perceive and treat the relation to nature. Umeå's environmental

documents encompass both human and non-human aspects. Many cities primarily view nature as a resource for humans or as a passive backdrop lacking all agency (as noted in works of Merchant 1980; Plumwood 1993). This anthropocentric view of nature is common and recognizes nature's value only through the usefulness and practical benefits of natural resources and ecosystems to humanity (Fremaux and Barry 2019; Goralnik and Nelson 2012). In Umeå we see both anthropocentric elements of this view of nature as a value to humans for example in relation to how nature provides health benefits, economic growth, city appeal, and community vitality. At the same time, the pivotal deviation from other municipalities is how Umeå's policies also assign significance to nature beyond such utilitarian aspects. This is acknowledged throughout the documents.

5.1.1 The value of nature and its linkage to the identity of the city

Umeå's climate policy articulates an intrinsic view of nature, recognizing the natural world's inherent worth beyond its utility to humans and society (Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2020, 16–18). This framing challenges the eco-modern logic observed in other Swedish municipalities where nature is often viewed instrumentally – as a passive resource for human advancement (see also Hagbert, Wangel, and Broms 2020). While Umeå's articulation does not fully reflect the philosophical complexity of intrinsic value (Devall and Sessions 1985; Cheney 1992), nor the varied way that it can be applied (Batavia and Nelson 2017), it gestures toward an ethical stance in which nature is seen as having agency and rights to exist and thrive on its own terms.

The framing is relevant in both language and content. The concept of “the intrinsic value of nature” appears almost as frequently as references to its human utility (21 and 28 times respectively). Policy documents emphasize the importance of ecological well-being for the health of people, animals, and plants (Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2022, 37), suggesting a more reciprocal view of humans-nature relations. It is significant from an ethical standpoint as this perspective encourages a deeper respect for the natural world and promotes the idea of conservation for the sake of preserving biodiversity and ecological balance. The detailed attention to wetlands, rare local plants, fish spawning grounds, biodiversity and even reindeer husbandry (Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2020, 17–21) reflects a broadened environmental ethic and potentially a more inclusive recognition of diverse ecological knowledges, including those relevant to Indigenous groups such as the Sami.

Umeå's identification with nature is further shaped by the city's geographic and historical context. Surrounded by forests and water, Umeå situates its sustainability agenda within what it calls “cultural environments” – a term that fuses natural and historical landscapes, as expressed in policy:

Living forests, rich agricultural landscapes, and other natural habitats create vital environments for diverse plant and animal life, forming an integral part of our history and cultural landscape (Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2020, 13).

This connection between nature and cultural identity fosters a sense of local stewardship and contributes to the municipality's normative commitment to conservation. As one respondent explained:

[T]here was a survey done [...] where they looked specifically at how aware and willing to, and there I know that Umeå stood out a bit in [...] linking very much one's own well-being and the city's development with maintaining a strong natural capital (Respondent U4, 2023).

Importantly, by linking ecological values to cultural heritage, Umeå's framing offers potential for disrupting entrenched nature-culture binaries and legitimizing plural ways of knowing in policymaking. This creates openings for more inclusive sustainability practices – provided these framings are not co-opted by economic growth imperatives. This gap between conceptual ambition and institutional practice reveals how intrinsic value framings, while ethically progressive, can face resistance within established governance structures. As intersectional and posthumanist perspectives highlight, such framings can only contribute to equity if they are embedded in inclusive processes that question whose relationships to nature are centred and whose knowledge systems are legitimized.

5.1.2 Conflicting views on nature

While Umeå's policy documents emphasize the intrinsic value of nature, they also repeatedly highlight the benefits of utilizing natural resources for human wellbeing, growth and attractiveness. This reflects a dual framing of nature – on one hand as inherently valuable, on the other as an asset to be strategically managed. Such internal contradictions are common in municipal policy, but they pose significant challenges in practice, particularly when documents fail to explicitly acknowledge or reconcile these tensions.

Unlike many other municipalities we have studied, Umeå often subordinates economic values to social and environmental goals. Rather than portraying economic growth as the main driver, ecological sustainability is framed as a foundation upon which economic benefits can emerge directly (Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2020). This suggests an attempt to move beyond a strictly eco-modern logic – in which technological innovation and market mechanisms are seen as solutions to environmental challenges (Mol and PJ 2003; Næss and Saglie 2019) – toward a more integrated sustainability narrative. However, the lack of guidance on how to resolve trade-offs between these objectives weakens the transformative potential of such vision.

This limitation was evident in our interviews. Respondents expressed concern over the absence of clear prioritizations when policy goals conflict. One interviewee critiqued the assumption that contradictory aims can simply be managed away:

We can say that we should preserve forests, and we should have growth. If you don't specify which of those trumps the other or at least have a dialogue about it, then you won't progress either (Respondent U4, 2023).

Another emphasized the political nature of these tensions, noting that municipalities are governed by elected officials, which can further complicate implementation when values or interests diverge (Respondent U1, 2023). Still others pointed out that ecological goals are sometimes overshadowed by population growth targets and business expansion, leading to the loss of green spaces (Respondent U2, 2023).

In this context, the municipality's preference for win-win framings – which suggest that ecological and economic objectives can be simultaneously achieved can obscure the underlying power dynamics and material trade-offs that shape urban development. As one respondent remarked:

[W]e need to move much more from testing and piloting to actually changing processes and that's the quite painful transition that needs to happen (Respondent U3, 2023).

This echoes insights from intersectional theory, which emphasize that conflicting institutional logics – such as bureaucratic growth imperatives versus environmental conservation – require more than technical coordination and management. They involve redistributive decision about space, resources, and priorities that inevitably produce winners and losers (cf. Acker 2006). Institutional efforts such as dedicated business services and the establishment of an industry council (Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2018) further signal commitment to growth. But without explicit mechanisms for prioritizing between competing goals, these strategies risk reinforcing eco-modern assumptions under a more progressive veneer.

In sum, while Umeå's policies elevate the intrinsic value of nature to a normative ideal, their reliance on ambiguous win-win framings and the absence of concrete governance tools to mediate trade-offs reveal important tensions. Our intersectional lens highlights how such tensions are not merely technical but inherently political and relational, involving competing claims over space, value and the future of the city.

The following chapter explores the intricate dynamics of social, human-to-human power relations within Umeå municipality's climate policy framework.

5.2 Social, human-to-human power relation

In this section we address the question of what categories of humans are deemed relevant to climate policy and its implementation? We scrutinize norms in policy around human relations and how they relate to ecological sustainability. We explored how Umeå municipality organizes and reproduces power dynamics in their climate policy by identifying concepts that highlight power relations, such as inclusion and justice. Inclusion refers to the extent to which diverse voices and perspectives are represented in decision-making processes, whereas justice pertains to the fair distribution of resources and opportunities. These concepts serve as lenses through which intersectional power dynamics can be analysed in a critical policy analysis.

Following Carol Bacchi (1999, 2010) we investigated how various social categories are discussed and framed in documents and interviews, discovering that the climate efforts reflect a systemic view connecting social and ecological sustainability. Efforts toward ecological sustainability are not perceived as isolated, but as interconnected with broader sustainability goals, emphasizing the interdependence of social and environmental aspects. However, policy documents predominantly discuss equity in broad terms, framed around universal benefits. Interviews provided a more nuanced approach to equity, discussing different social groups and their needs in greater detail.

Policy documents articulate and emphasize a notion of "social responsibility" (Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2020, 14). However, this responsibility is often expressed in vague and ambiguous terms, raising questions about who is responsible and whom this responsibility is owed. Notably, the concept is frequently framed as a duty directed toward other parts of the world. Umeå Municipality presents itself in policy documents as an international role model, aspiring to promote democratic development and build local capacities in countries such as Kenya and China through partnership

programs. Yet, these initiatives are typically framed in non-reciprocal terms, with little or no reference to mutual learning exchanges. Rather, the municipality positions itself as the expert entity aiming to enhance international awareness of sustainable practices in areas such as green technology and clean energy. This stance raises ethical concerns.

By adopting an educator stance, the municipality risks imposing external solutions that may not align with local contexts, potentially undermining the very communities it seeks to support. The lack of emphasis on reciprocity reinforces hierarchical relations and may obstruct the development of culturally sensitive and genuinely sustainable solutions. In academic literature, such one-directional models of knowledge transfer have been widely criticized for marginalizing local voices and impeding the co-creation of knowledge (Castán Broto and Neves Alves 2018; Collins 2019; Sievers et al. 2024). It is therefore crucial that Umeå re-evaluate this approach and instead adopt collaborative, dialogical models that emphasize mutual learning, respect indigenous knowledge, and foster authentic community empowerment.

5.2.1 Equity and equality framings in policy and interviews

To assess how human-to-human relations are framed in Umeå's policies, we conducted a keyword search of both policy documents and interview transcripts, focusing on terms like: equity, equality and justice (see Table 2). The results reveal interesting patterns in how these concepts are distributed and prioritized across different types of material.

Equality was the most frequently occurring term in the documents, particularly in the Agenda 2030, which explicitly emphasizes social sustainability alongside ecological and economic concerns. In contrast, justice and equity appeared 12 times across all policy documents, and just four times in interview transcripts. Meanwhile, in interviews, the term equality – largely framed in terms of gender – was mentioned 52 times. This disparity suggests that while gender equality has gained a degree of institutional traction, broader justice concerns are less clearly articulated or operationalized. Interviewees often referred to gender-disaggregated data as a key tool for embedding equity concerns into policy. One respondent noted:

Gender data, we have come a long way there. We have learned it and the advantage of having learned it is that and seeing that it has an effect, it makes it much easier for us to also include other parameters. [...] We are talking about the possibility of looking at interacting indicators, which is what is interesting (Respondent U4, 2023).

This points to a data-driven foundation for gender mainstreaming, which several officials perceived as an entry point for more expansive inclusivity. Gender equality, in this view, becomes a model case – a policy arena where institutional learning has occurred and where these tools are now being tested for broader application.

The results coming out of the work with gender mainstreaming as a foundation for policy decisions, with gender-related data, was identified as the most developed tool also for incorporating other social factors in climate policy. An interviewee explains it is

Table 2. Results of key word search.

Keywords	Mentions documents	Mentions interviews
"justice" (<i>rättvisa</i>)	12 (9 in <i>Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality]. 2022</i>)	4
"equality" (<i>jämställdhet</i>)	23 (20 in <i>Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2018</i>)	52

because gender mainstreaming encourages the consideration of interconnected social factors and thus, can overcome potential conflicts of interest in policy objectives (Respondent U2, 2023).

We interpret this pattern through the concept of a “spill-over effect”. Originating from economics spill-over refers to the unintended effects of an economic policy that thereby have impacts extending beyond its original scope (Kenton 2024). In our case, spill-over means that progress in one social domain (e.g. gender) is assumed to trigger advances in other domains (e.g. class, race, age). Thus, it can be a way to advance an intersectional approach.

However, from an intersectional perspective, the assumption that equity gains in one dimension will automatically extend to others is problematic. Anthias (2013) reminds us that social divisions are historically and contextually specific, and that systems of privilege and oppression intersect in non-linear, often contradictory ways. Institutional practices that rely on universal categories or assume alignment between equity concerns risk reproducing the very exclusions they seek to address.

Similar spill-over effects between ecological and social sustainability are articulated in policy documents. Discussions on equality and equity centre on the co-benefits of ecological sustainability, with ecological sustainability being an opportunity for social sustainability as a by-product. One document notes:

The work with the local environmental goals creates synergies between all sustainability aspects and promotes people’s physical and mental well-being (Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2020, 3).

Here, social sustainability is presented as a by-product of ecological well-being. This framing aligns with eco-modern assumptions that environmental progress will naturally yield social co-benefits, yet, risks depoliticizing social inequality by not addressing the structural conditions that shape vulnerability and participation. Pla-Julián and Guevara (2019) and Haase et al. (2017) argue, truly sustainable development must move beyond the pursuit of aligned goals or presumed synergies. It requires grappling with the ethical and distributive tensions between them and developing intentional strategies that recognize the complex interplay of power, identity and environment.

In Umeå, gender mainstreaming has opened important avenues for data use and institutional reflection. But for a more robust intersectional approach, equity must be treated not only as a functional goal or add-on benefit, but as a politically charged, relational dimension of climate governance – one that demands attention to competing interests, historical exclusions, and differentiated lived experiences.

5.2.2 Naming humans and groups

Our analysis of Umeå’s climate policy documents reveals the inclusion of several social groups, such as children, the elderly, and people with disabilities and to a lesser extent women, the indigenous Same people and the Finnish minority. These groups are often discussed in isolation or grouped under vague categories like “vulnerable”, without acknowledging the intersectional dimension of their experience. For instance:

Traffic safety and expanding public transportation [...], with particular attention to the needs of people in vulnerable situations, women, children, persons with disabilities, and older individuals (Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality] 2018, 25).

This one-size-fits-all risks flattening social difference, as it treats categories as additive rather than intersectional and relational. Interview respondents, however, displayed a more nuanced awareness. One explained: “The children’s perspective I think we can probably get even better at because there are a lot of benefits of raising that issue.” (Respondent U2, 2023), suggesting a more inclusive perspective as children have often been neglected in planning, and one that is looking toward future generations’ potential needs.

Explicit references to gender are surprisingly limited in the documents. There were 13 mentions across four texts in comparison to the high frequency of gender in interviews (49 mentions). The text analysis included terms such as “woman,” “women,” “gender,” “gender division,” and “gender equality” and we found that the main context in which gender was mentioned was in a phrase that repeated the formulation of the national gender legislation.⁸ The lack of inclusion of gender in documents might be the result of gender-related concerns being addressed elsewhere in the municipal context. Respondents explained that gender-disaggregated data is well incorporated in Umeå’s planning routines and perceived as a potential entry point for broader inclusion efforts:

I think we have been quite proficient regarding gender-disaggregated data. We have learned and incorporated it, using it as a tool in urban planning and decision-making processes. However, the other type of data is something we have only just started to explore; we need to become much better at incorporating it (Respondent U4, 2023).

Yet, the absence of gender in documents may also be due to an assumption that gender is less relevant in relation to sustainability and that gender, as with other social categories, is subsumed under the broader categories of social sustainability, equity or equality instead of delving into defining particular human groups. Established practices around gender mainstreaming are believed to facilitate attention to other social categories. Yet, assuming that efforts in one domain automatically enhance inclusion in others risks overlooking structural differences in how power and privilege are distributed across categories such as race, migration status, and class.

Indeed, ethnic and cultural diversity is almost entirely absent in policy documents. Keywords such as “ethnicity,” “immigration,” “immigrants,” “refugees,” “from other countries,” and “different backgrounds” appear only once across all texts. Respondents acknowledge this silence. One noted:

“What do people look like in these nice images? Are they white? Are they Black? Do they have disabilities?” (Respondent U2, 2023).

This comment points to the visual and discursive reproduction of whiteness as the norm in municipal planning. Another respondent reflected critically on how dominant norms shape urban development:

When planning and building the city, who are you building it for? Who is the norm when developing a neighborhood or park, for instance? It is clear that we have a very, very strong norm perspective on how we have done things. It feels like it is the middle-aged man who is always the focus. Whereas when we bring in other perspectives, gender equality, children’s perspective, or something else, then it becomes something entirely different (Respondent U4, 2023).

From an institutional intersectionality lens (cf. Acker 2006; Winker and Degele 2011), this pattern illustrates how power operates not only through the inclusion or exclusion of

social categories, but through the norms, routines, and visual language of policy institutions. Despite the silence on ethnic diversity in policy documents, through interviews we found that municipal officials recognize the importance of diversity and inclusivity. Our respondents emphasized the need to incorporate other cultural aspects more deeply and reflects an understanding of the importance of knowledge related to diverse cultural backgrounds and life experiences and indicates a recognition of the value of comprehending diversity within the city. Despite individual awareness among officials, these insights are not yet institutionalized in planning frameworks or explicitly addressed.

5.3 The challenges and opportunities for inclusive policy processes

Our analysis of Umeå's climate policy reveals a divergence between how equity is framed in formal policy documents and how it is understood by individual policy makers. While the documents largely rely on universalist framings of social benefit – implying that climate action will serve “everyone” – the interviews show more critical awareness of social differentiations and the unequal distribution of power. Interviewees acknowledged that equity is not evenly distributed across groups, and that some residents contribute more to emissions while others are more vulnerable to their effects. One respondent reflected critically on how policy must account for these disparities:

We [Respondent and colleagues in the same role] are supposed to oversee and ensure that the perspective of the residents of Umeå municipality is included. [...] What does it mean for different groups of residents, and what consequences might it have? [...] We need to dare to say that certain groups account for greater emissions than others. This has to do with power and privileges. And to make connections visible between who has the power to decide what should be done, who is supposed to enforce the change, and what discrepancies might there be between them (Respondent U3, 2023).

Although policy documents did not deliver such insights, individual policy makers acknowledged systemic injustices and recognized power relations between different social groups. Yet, when social groups were discussed, the tendency was to discuss each group separately and the spotlight was often on gender. This may obscure potential conflicts between the needs of different groups and overlook the intersecting identities and experiences of individuals.

As Arora-Jonsson and Wahlström's (2023) argue, this tendency to treat social categories like gender as homogeneous risks masking intersecting inequalities – such as class, ethnicity, or age – and ignoring the broader socio-economic and political contexts in which policy is formulated and implemented. Our findings confirm that while gender is relatively institutionalized in Umeå's policy landscape, other axes of difference remain under-addressed. One respondent expressed this:

So, we really must learn about interconnected indicators. We should actually put them in relation to each other to a much greater extent. This could be age aspects, origin, etc. (Respondent U4, 2023).

This reflects an emerging but not yet fully realized recognition of intersectionality, that social categories do not exist in isolation and must be analysed relationally.

Drawing on Acker (2006) and Winker and Degele's (2011) institutional perspective, we interpret these insights as evidence that while individual actors may acknowledge complexity, institutional practices lag behind in operationalizing it. Crucially, making equity meaningful in climate governance requires more than better data or expanded indicators. It call for what scholars such as Collins (2019) and Magnusdottir and Kronsell (2023) describe as reflexive institutional practices: ongoing internal dialogues about who holds power, whose knowledge counts, and which voices are heard and which are excluded. For this to happen, policy processes must create spaces for critical reflection on how decisions are made, by whom and with what effect.

In sum, while Umeå demonstrates growing awareness of the need for inclusive climate policy, particularly based on its work on gender, advancing a genuinely intersectional approach demands a shift from a single-axis to a multidimensional inclusion in governance. This includes recognizing power relations not only in society but also within the institutions – in their practices, assumptions and ways of knowing.

6. Concluding discussion

This article employed a critical intersectional analysis to explore how power relations – both between humans and nature, and among human groups – are perceived in climate policy and interpreted by policy makers. We found that Umeå's approach to sustainability stands out for its emphasis on the intrinsic value of nature. This perspective prioritizes the inherent worth of nature beyond its utilitarian benefits. Despite the emphasis on nature's intrinsic value and its connection to Umeå's local identity, tensions emerged when ecological values conflict with economic objectives. While the documents express a commitment to win-win scenarios, the interviews reveal that to balance these priorities is tricky and not always achieved.

Both policy documents and expert interviews discussed various ways to incorporate diverse knowledges. Interview participants expressed concerns about unequal participation in the policy process and emphasized the importance of greater inclusion. However, it remains unclear to what extent diverse knowledges are reflected in the policy documents or influence implementation – an area beyond the scope of this article.

Our material pointed to a general awareness of gender aspects. Policy makers conveyed that it was based on a long-standing commitment to gender integration and were of the conviction that previous efforts on gender equality – particularly in the inclusion of new types of knowledge and data – could spill-over and pave the way for the consideration of other social groups, such as indigenous or migrant groups. Thus, addressing one type of inequity can serve as the foundation for broader diversity initiatives. Yet, this is conditional and will only occur if intersectional practices are institutionalized. The spill-over effect may help or hinder depending on assumptions embedded in policy practices.

The case of Umeå illustrates that gender mainstreaming can serve as a foundation and a stepping stone for broader inclusion of diverse groups, voices and knowledges. We noted efforts to address equity concerns and saw signs of an acknowledgment of systemic injustices among our respondents. However, our analysis showed that Umeå still has work to do in incorporating diverse perspectives, addressing power imbalances and explicitly discussing potential conflicts of interest in municipal policy goals. Incorporating intersectional theory into climate policy can enhance equity by promoting a more nuanced and inclusive

approach to address social inequalities and injustices related to environmental and climate issues. This is likely to increase its effectiveness when implemented in society. Such an approach necessarily involves incorporating diverse perspectives and knowledges more comprehensively into policy documents and decision-making processes. At the same time, gender mainstreaming needs to be approached with caution to avoid oversimplification of social issues. This, in order to prevent misdirected outcomes stemming from focusing solely on universal benefits or on one social category, such as gender, without understanding the complex social system in which it exists. Such initiatives may fail to comprehensively address the needs of marginalized groups.

Based on the insights from the case of Umeå municipality we have identified several avenues for future research. There is a need to investigate how intersectionality-informed climate policies can be implemented in practice and how to navigate and overcome institutional path dependencies that hinders a holistic approach to social and ecological sustainability. We see a need to expand the analysis of human-nature and human-human relations to other “most likely cases” (municipalities). This includes identifying if and how diverse knowledges and perspectives are integrated in climate policies. Through such comparative studies, best practices could potentially be identified. A related avenue for future research is to further investigate the limitations and opportunities of gender mainstreaming efforts, in Umeå and beyond, and whether such efforts have led to the inclusion of other social groups in climate policy.

In sum, Umeå’s policy framework presents a compelling vision of sustainability that integrates both ecological and social dimensions. This study has demonstrated the necessity of intersectionality not only as an analytical tool but also as a guiding principle for inclusive policy-making. While the findings are grounded in a specific context, the challenges, strategies and opportunities identified here hold relevance beyond Umeå – offering valuable insights for advancing both intersectional research and inclusive and equitable climate governance in other settings.

Notes

1. Climate and environmental governance in Europe is in line with ecological modernization or eco-modernization (Jänicke and Jacob 2004; Mol 2003; Næss and Saglie 2019). It is based on the idea that the economy constantly develops to become ever more efficient with the help of new (technological) innovations that benefit the market. The underlying idea is that the economy can continue to grow while the climate effects are contained and reduced. Thus, economic growth is perceived as a welfare creator and it includes a great deal of optimism about what the market can achieve.
2. funded by the Swedish Research Council (FORMAS) Project # FR-2018/0010
3. such as Vinnova, the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, the Swedish Transport Administration, and the Swedish Energy Agency
4. Compared with the two cities we studied before, Malmö and Gothenburg.
5. Statistics Sweden <https://www.scb.se/en/> https://www.scb.se/contentassets/3d0757be0f7140dca08072f18dd99ff3/be0701_2023a01_br_be51br2305.pdf Accessed 20240924
6. European Commission. (2020). EU Social Progress Index 2020. Retrieved from <https://cohesiondata.ec.europa.eu/stories/s/EU-Social-Progress-Index-2020/8qk9-xq96>
7. For example in the European Green Deal (EC 2019)
8. <https://www.regeringen.se/regeringens-politik/jamstalldhet/mal-for-jamstalldhet/> Accessed September 25, 2024.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

The research for this study was financed through the Swedish Research Council Formas grant number [FR2018/0010]. We have used ChatGPTedu4 to assist with language and grammar of the article text.

References

- Acker, Joan. 2006. "Inequality Regimes: Gender, Class, and Race in Organizations." *Gender and Society* 20 (4): 441–464. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891243206289499>.
- Amrén, Joel, and Johannes Hedfors. 2023. "Achieving Zero Emission Transportation in a Regional Perspective. Addressing Municipal Climate Goals in Umeå." Master, Gothenburg: Chalmers University of Technology. <https://odr.chalmers.se/server/api/core/bitstreams/52f3dd99-0a02-4919-93ec-1775127ab9b1/content>.
- Anthias, Floya. 2013. "Intersectional What? Social Divisions, Intersectionality and Levels of Analysis." *Ethnicities* 13 (1): 3–19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468796812463547>.
- Arora-Jonsson, Seema. 2011. "Virtue and Vulnerability: Discourses on Women, Gender and Climate Change." *Global Environmental Change* 21 (2): 744–751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2011.01.005>.
- Arora-Jonsson, Seema, and Nora Wahlström. 2023. "Unraveling the Production of Ignorance in Climate Policymaking: The Imperative of a Decolonial Feminist Intervention for Transformation." *Environmental Science and Policy* 149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.103564>.
- Bacchi, Carol. 1999. *Women, Policy and Politics. The Construction of Policy Problems*. London: Sage: London.
- Bacchi, Carol. 2012. "Why Study Problematizations? Making Politics Visible." *Open Journal of Political Science* 02 (01): 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojps.2012.21001>.
- Bacchi, Carol, and Joan Eveline. 2010. "What Are We Mainstreaming When We Mainstream Gender?" *Mainstreaming Politics: Gendering Practices and Feminist Theory*, 2005, 87–109. <https://doi.org/10.1017/UPO9780980672381.008>.
- Batavia, Chelsea., and Michael Paul Nelson. (2017). For Goodness Sake! What is Intrinsic Value and why Should we Care? *Biological Conservation*, 209, 366–376. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2017.03.003>
- Bradley, Karin. 2009. "Planning for Eco-Friendly Living in Diverse Societies." *Local Environment* 14 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549830902764738>.
- Brundtland, Gro Harlem. 1987. "Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future." *Oxford Paperbacks* Report of:400. <http://www.un-documents.net/wced-ocf.htm>.
- Bulkeley, Harriet. 2010. "Cities and the Governing of Climate Change." *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* 35 (1): 229–253. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-072809-101747>.
- Bulkeley, Harriet, and Kristine Kern. 2006. "Local Government and the Governing of Climate Change in Germany and the UK." *Urban Studies* 43 (12): 2237–2259. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00420980600936491>.
- Castán Broto, Vanesa, and Harriet Bulkeley. 2013. "A Survey of Urban Climate Change Experiments in 100 Cities." *Global Environmental Change* 23 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2012.07.005>.
- Castán Broto, V. and Neves Alves, S. (2018) Intersectionality Challenges for the Coproduction of Urban Services: Notes for a Theoretical and Methodological Agenda. *Environment and Urbanization*, 30 (2). 367–386. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956247818790208>

- Castán Broto, Vanesa, and Linda Westman. 2019. *Urban Sustainability and Justice: Just Sustainabilities and Environmental Planning*. London: Zed Books.
- Cheney, Jim. 1992. "Intrinsic Value in Environmental Ethics: Beyond Subjectivism and Objectivism." *The Monist* 75 (2): 227–235.
- Collier, Ute. 1997. "Local Authorities and Climate Protection in the European Union: Putting Subsidiarity Into Practice?" *Local Environment* 2 (1): 39–57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839708725511>.
- Collins, Patricia Hill. 2019. *Intersectionality as Critical Social Theory*. Duke University Press.
- Collins, Patricia Hill, and Sirma Bilge. 2016. *Intersectionality*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Cuomo, Chris J. 2011. "Climate Change, Vulnerability, and Responsibility." *Hypatia* 26 (4): 690–714. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1527-2001.2011.01220.x>.
- Devall, Bill, and George Sessions. 1985. *Deep Ecology*. South Africa, G.M. Smith.
- EC. 2019. "The European Green Deal." European Commission 53 (9): 24. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52019DC0640&from=EN>.
- Emelianoff, Cyria. 2014. "Local Energy Transition and Multilevel Climate Governance: The Contrasted Experiences of Two Pioneer Cities (Hanover, Germany, and Växjö, Sweden)." *Urban Studies* 51 (7): 1378–1393. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098013500087>.
- Finn, D., and L. McCormick. 2011. "Urban Climate Change Plans: How Holistic?" *Local Environment* 16 (4): 397–416.
- Fremaux, Anne, and John Barry. 2019. "The 'Good Anthropocene' and Green Political Theory: Rethinking Environmentalism, Resisting Ecomodernism." In *Anthropocene Encounters: New Directions in Green Political Thinking*, 171–190. Cambridge University Press.
- Gaard, Greta. 2010. "New Directions for Ecofeminism: Toward a More Feminist Ecocriticism." *Interdisciplinary Studies in Literature and Environment* 17 (4): 643–665. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isle/isq108>.
- Gaard, Greta. 2011. "Ecofeminism Revisited: Rejecting Essentialism and Re-Placing Species in a Material Feminist Environmentalism." *Feminist Formations* 23 (2): 26–53. <https://doi.org/10.1353/ff.2011.0017>.
- Godfrey, Phoebe, and Denise Torres. 2016. *Systemic Crises of Global Climate Change: Intersections of Race, Class and Gender*. London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315737454>.
- Goralnik, L., and M. P. Nelson. 2012. "Anthropocentrism." In *Encyclopaedia of Applied Ethics*, edited by R. Chadwick, 145–155. Elsevier.
- Haase, Dagmar, Sigrun Kabisch, Annegret Haase, Erik Andersson, Ellen Banzhaf, Francesc Baró, Miriam Brenck, et al. 2017. "Greening Cities – To Be Socially Inclusive? About the Alleged Paradox of Society and Ecology in Cities." *Habitat International* 64: 41–48. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2017.04.005>.
- Hagbert, Pernilla, Josefin Wangel, and Looove Broms. 2020. "Exploring the Potential for Just Urban Transformations in Light of Eco-Modernist Imaginaries of Sustainability." *Urban Planning* 5 (4): 204–216. <https://doi.org/10.17645/up.v5i4.3302>.
- Hess, David J., and Rachel G. McKane. 2021. "Making Sustainability Plans More Equitable: An Analysis of 50 U.S. Cities." *Local Environment* 26 (4): 461–476. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2021.1892047>.
- IPCC [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change]. 2018. "Global Warming of 1.5°C: An IPCC Special Report." Link.
- IPCC Report, IPCC. 2022. "Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Summary for Policymakers. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change." *United Nations Environment Programme UNEP AR6*.
- Jänicke, Martin, and Klaus Jacob. 2004. "Lead Markets for Environmental Innovations: A New Role for the Nation State Lead Markets for Environmental Innovations: A New Role for the Nation State" 4 (1): 29–46.
- Kaijser, Anna, and Annica Kronsell. 2014. "Climate Change Through the Lens of Intersectionality." *Environmental Politics* 23 (3): 417–433. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2013.835203>.
- Kenton, Will. 2024. What Is the Spillover Effect and How Does It Affect Economies? Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/spillover-effect.asp>.

- Kern, Kristine. 2019. "Cities as Leaders in EU Multilevel Climate Governance: Embedded Upscaling of Local Experiments in Europe." *Environmental Politics* 28 (1): 125–145. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2019.1521979>.
- Khan, Jamil, Roger Hildingsson, and Lisa Garting. 2020. "Sustainable Welfare in Swedish Cities: Challenges of Eco-Social Integration in Urban Sustainability Governance." *Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12010383>.
- Klinsky, Sonja, Timmons Roberts, Saleemul Huq, Chukwumerije Okereke, Peter Newell, Peter Dauvergne, Karen O'Brien, et al. 2017. "Why Equity Is Fundamental in Climate Change Policy Research." *Global Environmental Change*. Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.08.002>.
- Kronsell, Annica. 2024. "Imagining a New Gender Contract for Climate." In *Imagining a New Gender Equality Contract: Feminism as a Progressive Glue*, edited by Thissen Petö. Foundation for European Progressive Studies.
- Kronsell, Annica, L. Gunnhildur Magnúsdóttir, Nanna Rask, and Benedict Singleton. 2023. "An Intersectional Exploration of Climate Institutions." In *The Oxford Handbook of Comparative Environmental Politics*, edited by J. Sowers, S. VanDeveer, and E. Weinthal, 223–239. Oxford University Press.
- Laestander, Nygren Tilly. 2024. "(Just) Transition Toward Climate Neutrality - A Case Study on Umeå." Master, Malmö University. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1866100/FULLTEXT02>.
- Lundgren, Angelica. 2022. "The Siloed Umbrella: An Intersectional Reading of Climate Policy in Malmö, Sweden." Master's Thesis, University of Gothenburg.
- Lundqvist, Lennart J, and Sjur Kasa. 2016. "Between National Soft Regulations and Strong Economic Incentives: Local Climate and Energy Strategies in Sweden" 0568 (October): 0–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2016.1197827>.
- Lykke, Nina. 2010. *Feminist Studies: A Guide to Intersectional Theory, Methodology and Writing*. *Feminist Studies: A Guide to Intersectional Theory, Methodology and Writing*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203852774>.
- Magnúsdóttir, Gunnhildur L, and Annica Kronsell. 2021. *Gender, Intersectionality and Climate Institutions in Industrialized States*. RoutledgeEarthscan.
- Magnúsdóttir, Gunnhildur L, and Annica Kronsell. 2023. "Climate Institutions Matter: The Challenges of Making Gender-Sensitive and Inclusive Climate Policies." *Cooperation and Conflict* 59(3).
- Merchant, Carolyn. 1980. *The Death of Nature. Women, Ecology and the Scientific Revolution*. San Francisco.: Harper.
- Mol, Arthur P.J. 2003. *Globalization and Environmental Reform: The Ecological Modernization of the Global Economy*. MIT Press.
- Mummery, Jane, and Josephine Mummery. 2019. "Transformative Climate Change Adaptation: Bridging Existing Approaches with Post-Foundational Insights on Justice." *Local Environment* 24 (10): 919–930. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2019.1656180>.
- Næss, Petter, and Inger-Lise Saglie. 2019. "Ecological Modernisation." In *The Routledge Companion to Environmental Planning*, 63–72. Routledge.
- O'Donnell, Emerald, and Andréanne Doyon. 2023. "Language, Context, and Action: Exploring Equity and Justice Content in Vancouver Environmental Plans." *Local Environment* 28 (11): 1478–1495. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2023.2238734>.
- Otto, Antje, Kristine Kern, Wolfgang Haupt, Peter Eckersley, and Annegret H Thieken. 2021. "Ranking Local Climate Policy: Assessing the Mitigation and Adaptation Activities of 104 German Cities." *Climatic Change* 167 (5). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-021-03142-9>.
- Persson, Vilhelm. 2013. "Sweden: Local Government in Sweden: Flexibility and Independence in a Unitary State." In *Local Government in Europe*, 305–329. Routledge.
- Pla-Julián, Isabel, and Sandra Guevara. 2019. "Is Circular Economy the Key to Transitioning Towards Sustainable Development? Challenges from the Perspective of Care Ethics." *Futures* 105 (January):67–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUTURES.2018.09.001>.
- Plumwood, Val. 1993. *Feminism and the Mastery of Nature*. Routledge.
- Rask, Nanna. 2022. "An Intersectional Reading of Circular Economy Policies: Towards Just and Sufficiency-Driven Sustainabilities." *Local Environment* 27 (10–11). <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2022.2040467>.

- Rask, Nanna, Angelica Lundgren, and Annica Kronsell. 2025. "(Applying) Intersectionality in Climate Policy and Planning: Experiences from Gothenburg and Malmö." In *Towards a Feminist Climate Policy in Industrialised States: What Would a Feminist Climate Policy Look Like, and How Will We Get There?*, edited by S. Buckingham, M. Hultman, G. LMorrow, and K. Magnusdottir. Routledge.
- Rådet för främjande av kommunala analyser (RKA). 2022. "RKA Kolada Database." www.Kolada.se. 2022.
- Schlosberg, David. 2013. "Theorising Environmental Justice : The Expanding Sphere of a Discourse," no. February 2014, 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2013.755387>.
- Shabb, Katherine, and Kes McCormick. 2023. "Achieving 100 Climate Neutral Cities in Europe: Investigating Climate City Contracts in Sweden." <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-023-00035-8>.
- Sievers, Eva., Marja Spierenburg, Shivant S. Jhagroe and Alexander P.E. van Oudenhoven. 2024. "Place-based Knowledge Transfer in a Local-to-Global and Knowledge-to-Action Context: Key Steps and Facilitative Factors." *Ecology and Society*, 29(3). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-15024-290308>
- Singleton, Benedict, and Gunnhildur L. Magnusdottir. 2021. "Take a Ride Into the Danger Zone? Assessing Path Dependency and the Possibilities for Instituting Change at Two Swedish Government Agencies Earthscan." In *Gender, Intersectionality and Climate Institutions in Industrialized States*, edited by Gunnhildur L Magnusdottir, and Annica Kronsell, 86–102. London: Earthscan, Routledge.
- Singleton, Benedict, Nanna Rask, Gunnhildur Magnusdottir, and Annica Kronsell. 2022. "Intersectionality and Climate Policy Making: The Inclusion of Social Difference by Three Swedish Government Agencies." *Environmental and Planning C: Politics and Space* 40 (1): 180–200.
- Sippel, Maike, and Till Jenssen. 2009. "What about Local Climate Governance ? A Review of Promise and Problems What about Local Climate Governance ? A Review of Promise and Problems," Available at SSRN: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=15143341-51.
- Thomas, Kimberley, R. Dean Hardy, Heather Lazrus, Michael Mendez, Ben Orlove, Isabel Rivera-Collazo, J. Timmons Roberts, Marcy Rockman, Benjamin P. Warner, and Robert Winthrop. 2019. "Explaining Differential Vulnerability to Climate Change: A Social Science Review." *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*. Wiley-Blackwell. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.565>.
- Thompson, Charis, and Sherilyn MacGregor. 2017. "The Death of Nature. Foundations of Ecological Feminist Thought." In *Routledge Handbook of Gender and Environmnet*, edited by Sherilyn MacGregor, 43–53. Milton Park: Routledge, Earthscan.
- Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality]. 2018. "Agenda 2030 i Umeå Kommun: Kartläggning Av Arbetet Med Agenda 2030 [Mapping of Umeå's Work with Agenda 2030]." <https://www.umea.se/hallbaraumea/saarbetarvi/agenda2030iumea.4.408bf0f717442258a88c50.html>.
- Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality]. 2020. "Umeås Lokala Miljömål 2020 [Umeå Local Environmental Objectives 2020]." <https://www.umea.se/byggaboochmiljo/samhallsutvecklingochhallbarhet/klimatmiljoochhallbarhet/strategisktmiljoarbete/miljomal.4.5bc0956b1719ab0ae7f6b.html>.
- Umeå Kommun [Umeå Municipality]. 2022. "Umeå Klimatfärdplan: Ett Gemensamt Arbeta För Umeås Klimatomställning 2023–2025 [Umeå Climate Action Programme 2023-2025]." <https://www.umea.se/byggaboochmiljo/samhallsutvecklingochhallbarhet/klimatmiljoochhallbarhet/umeaklimatfardplan.4.208bd9441815d63c3d8252.html>.
- Vanhuyse, Fedra, Shogofa Rezaie, Mathilda Englund, Julia Jokiaho, Maryna Henrysson, and Karin André. 2022. "Including the Social in the Circular: A Mapping of the Consequences of a Circular Economy Transition in the City of Umeå, Sweden." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 380 (134893).
- Westman, Linda, and Vanesa Castán Broto. 2021. "Local Environment Transcending Existing Paradigms: The Quest for Justice in Urban Climate Change Planning." <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2021.1916903>.
- Winker, Gabriele, and Nina Degele. 2011. "Intersectionality as Multi-Level Analysis: Dealing with Social Inequality." *European Journal of Women's Studies* 18 (1): 51–66. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1350506810386084>.
- Yuval-Davis, Nira. 2006. "Intersectionality and Feminist Politics." *European Journal of Women's Studies* 13 (3): 193–209.